

ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF PERCEIVED VALUE, USER SATISFACTION, SERVICE QUALITY & SWITCHING COSTS ON USER LOYALTY OF B2B PLATFORM E-COMMERCE APPLICATIONS

NADIA MIRANDA EFFENDI PUTRI¹ and FARIDA INDRIYANI²

^{1,2}Universitas Diponegoro, Semarang, East Java, Indonesia.

Abstract

In the face of increasingly fierce business competition, the success of a company is highly dependent on the long-term strategy of a company. One of them is by increasing perceived value, user satisfaction, service quality and switching costs to increase User Loyalty. The population in this study is entrepreneurs (companies and individuals) who have used or are still using the B2B e-commerce platform, with a usage range of 1 – 5 years, and took a sample of 125 respondents using purposive sampling techniques. The data analysis technique in this study is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) and SPSS software is used as an analysis tool. The results of the study show that there is a significant influence between user satisfaction and service quality on the loyalty of users of b2b platform e-commerce applications. Meanwhile, Perceived Value and Switching Cost showed no significant effect on the loyalty of users of e-commerce applications on b2b platforms.

Keywords: Perceived Value, User Satisfaction, Service Quality Dan Switching Cost, User Loyalty.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the face of a highly competitive and challenging environment, the success of a company is highly dependent on the long-term strategy of the company and the relationship of mutualism with online application platforms and knowing the needs and interests of the company, it will be the core concept of the company in meeting the needs. Marketing a product in the context of B2B can be done through e-marketplaces, which can be used as a platform to increase cycle efficiency for buyers and sellers. Some of the B2B platforms are Ralali.com, Bizzy, Indonetwork and others (Muhammad, et.al 2021). On the other hand, the B2B platform is certainly less famous than B2C platforms such as Lazada, Tokopedia, Bukalapak and so on. The concept of the B2B platform is to bring together suppliers with business people.

Products or services naturally hold their own "value" in the eyes of consumers or users. Some products or services may be considered beneficial by certain individuals, while others may find them less useful, depending on the perceived value to the users. One commonly used B2B platform is Ralali, a leading Business-to-Business (B2B) e-commerce platform in Indonesia. It is committed to providing procurement solutions for Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). This platform is designed to facilitate transactions while driving business growth through user-friendly services and modern technology. However, Ralali.com has also received some negative reviews regarding its application. Despite this, according to its website, Ralali.com reports having approximately 8 million users across 12 industries, with 1.8 million transactions since its establishment in 2013. This makes Ralali.com one of the more popular platforms compared to other B2B platforms.

Loyalty to purchases through B2B platforms is described as a long-term relationship, leading to future use and user recommendations (Martensen & Grønholdt, 2003). In addition to user loyalty, perceived value or so-called perceived value also supports purchases through B2B platforms, because the value of an item itself also determines the purchase in a company. Satisfaction reflects the overall user experience when using a service or product.

Satisfaction is formed as a result of various interactions with the system. If users are not satisfied with their experience, they may stop using it (Akter et al., 2013). Research related to e-commerce concluded that trust has a positive and significant effect on user satisfaction levels. Cost also affects user loyalty. Burnham, et al., (2013) who have been referred to by Isaac and Luthfi (2011:56) said that switching costs occur when consumers switch from a product or service that they are currently using to the products or services of other companies or competitors. In addition to the factors that have been mentioned, service quality is also very important in building user loyalty on B2B e-commerce platforms.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1 Literature Review

2.1.1 *The Theory of Planned Behavior*

TPB adds an element of perceived behavioral control, which is an individual's perception of the ease or difficulty in carrying out an action. This TPB model is designed as an improvement of TRA by incorporating elements of perceived behavioral control, which aims to provide more precise predictions regarding the individual's behavioral intentions, especially in situations where the individual does not have full control over his actions (Ajzen, 1991).

2.1.2 *Perceived Value*

Perceived value is an important concept in marketing that refers to the way consumers value the benefits obtained from a product, compared to the costs or sacrifices they make, as explained by (Tjiptono, 2014).

2.1.3 *User Satisfaction*

User Satisfaction is a measure of the extent to which a product's performance can meet or even exceed buyer expectations. Thus, satisfaction is achieved when customers feel that the product or service they receive meets or exceeds the expectations they have set beforehand (Kotler & Keller, 2013:150),

2.1.4 *Service Quality*

Zeithaml et al. (1990) stated that service quality is an evaluation made by customers of the services they receive, by comparing them with the expectations they have. It involves the customer's perception of how the service meets the expectations they have set based on previous experience, the information they receive, and recommendations from others.

2.1.5 *Switching Costs*

According to Patel, Lillie, and Singh (2022), the switching cost is a cost that sooner or later will be faced by customers in the process of moving from one product or service to another. This can include direct or indirect costs, such as the time spent observing new products and services, comparing the two products and deterioration in the quality of experience when using other products.

2.1.6 *User Loyalty*

User loyalty can be understood as a deep commitment to a brand or distributor, which is reflected in consistent purchasing behavior (Tjiptono, 2008)

2.2 *Hypothesis Development*

Perceived value is a view of how a customer can or is able to see a benefit and a value of a product or service. The value can be assessed in various ways, such as cheaper cost, superior quality or higher social status are often the main attractions. Satisfaction reflects the overall user experience when using a service or product. Satisfaction is formed as a result of various interactions. If users are not satisfied with their experience, they may stop using it (Akter et al., 2013). Research related to e-commerce concluded that trust has a positive and significant effect on user satisfaction levels. According to Ratnasari & Akxa (2011) in Pereira et al. (2016), companies in the service trade sector need to continue to improve the quality of services. The importance of this lies in the ability of quality service to improve customer satisfaction, which in turn has a positive impact on their loyalty. Cost also affects user loyalty. Burnham, et al., (2013) who have been referred to by Isaac and Luthfi (2011:56) said that switching costs occur when consumers switch from a product or service that they are currently using to the products or services of other companies or competitors.

Haruna et al. (2017) assert that user loyalty is important because the ultimate goal of a company is to maintain user loyalty, get word-of-mouth promotions, and referrals, leading to increased customers. In line with research conducted by (Chuah et al., 2017; Deng et al., 2010; Hsu, 2014; Lam et al., 2004; Ray et al., 2012), which featured perceived value, customer satisfaction, and switching costs as the main driving factors. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed.

H1 = Perceived value has a positive effect on user satisfaction on *ecommerce* platform B2B

H2 = *perceived value* has a positive effect on user loyalty on *ecommerce* platform B2B

H3 = *service quality* has a positive effect on *user satisfaction* on *ecommerce* platform B2B

H4 = *service quality* has a positive effect on user loyalty on *ecommerce* platform B2B

H5 = *user satisfaction* has a positive effect on user loyalty on *ecommerce* platform B2B

H6 = *user satisfaction* has a positive effect on *switching cost* on *ecommerce* platform B2B

H7 = *switching costs* has a positive effect on user loyalty on *ecommerce* platform B2B

3. METHODOLOGY

The method in this study uses a quantitative method approach, the determined population is Entrepreneurs (Companies and Individuals) who have or are still using B2B e-commerce platforms. The sample criteria set in this study are Entrepreneurs (Companies and Individuals) who have or are still using the B2B e-commerce platform, with a usage range of 1 – 5 years. Because the population is unknown or non-probable, the sampling technique uses a purposive sampling technique with a research sample of 125 respondents. The data analysis technique used is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) and SPSS software is used as an analysis tool. The data assembly technique to obtain primary data used by researchers through questionnaires with measurements using interval scales.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results in this study answer the research question and analyze the relationship in the structural model. The coefficient of influence between variables is assessed using the values of person correlation and sig (2-tailed), as shown in the following table 1:

Table 1: Results of Relationship between Variables

	<i>Pearson Correlation</i>	<i>Sig. (2-tailed)</i>	Korelasi	Signifikansi
<i>Perceived value</i> – User Loyalty	0,672	0,082	Positive	Insignificant
<i>User Satisfaction</i> -User Loyalty	0,743	0,005	Positive	Significant
<i>Switching Costs</i> – User Loyalty	0,805	0,063	Positive	Insignificant
<i>Service Quality</i> – User Loyalty	0,765	0,047	Positive	Significant

The Relationship between *Perceived Value* and User Loyalty

In this study, hypothesis 2 (H2) states that there is a positive influence between perceived value and user loyalty. Based on the results of the test using SPSS software, the Pearson correlation (r) value of 0.672 indicates a strong positive correlation between the two variables. This interpretation conforms to the correlation coefficient guideline, where r values that are in the range of 0.50 to 0.70 are categorized as strong correlations. However, the value of Sig. (2-tailed) obtained is 0.082, a value greater than 0.05. This indicates that the correlation is not statistically significant. Thus, hypothesis 1 in this study is unacceptable. Although there is a strong positive relationship between the two variables with a Pearson correlation (r) value that shows a numerically strong relationship, the Sig. (2-tailed) value indicates that the correlation is not statistically significant, so the relationship between perceived value and user loyalty cannot be declared empirically significant in this study. Therefore, hypothesis 2 does not meet the requirements of statistical significance and is unacceptable in the context of a B2B e-commerce platform..

The Relationship between Service Quality and User Loyalty

In this study, Hypothesis 4 (H4) states that there is a relationship between service quality and user loyalty. Based on the test results using SPSS software, the Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.765 indicates a strong positive relationship between service quality and user loyalty. The positive correlation suggests that improvements in service quality will be followed by an

increase in user loyalty. The p-value (Sig. 2-tailed) of 0.047 is below the significance threshold of 0.05. Based on this finding, the relationship between these two variables is statistically significant. Thus, hypothesis 4 which states that there is an influence between service quality and user loyalty is acceptable. This means that improving better service quality will contribute to increasing user loyalty to the application of the B2B e-commerce platform. The positive and strong correlation between these two variables provides empirical evidence that service quality affects user loyalty. The p-value obtained (0.047) shows that the relationship between service quality and user loyalty is statistically significant, which further strengthens the finding that improving service quality can encourage user loyalty on B2B e-commerce platforms.

The Relationship between User Satisfaction and User Loyalty

Hypothesis 5 (H5) in the study states that there is a positive effect of user satisfaction on user loyalty. Based on the test results using SPSS software, the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) of 0.743 indicates a very strong positive relationship between the two variables. This interpretation aligns with the correlation coefficient guidelines, where an r-value in the range of 0.70 to 1.00 is categorized as a very strong correlation. The obtained Sig. (2-tailed) value is 0.005, which is less than 0.05. This indicates that the correlation is statistically significant, confirming that the relationship between user satisfaction and user loyalty is empirically significant in this study. Thus, Hypothesis 5, which posits a positive effect of user satisfaction on user loyalty, is accepted. This means that higher levels of user satisfaction contribute to an increase in user loyalty towards the B2B e-commerce platform Ralali. The statistically significant correlation provides empirical evidence that user satisfaction is a factor influencing user loyalty in the context of the Ralali B2B e-commerce platform.

The Relationship between Switching Costs and User Loyalty

In this study, hypothesis 7 (H7) states that there is a relationship between switching costs and user loyalty. Based on the results of the test using SPSS software, the Pearson correlation (r) value of 0.805 indicates a very strong positive correlation between the two variables. This interpretation is in accordance with the correlation coefficient guideline, where the r value which is in the range of 0.70 to 1.00 is categorized as a very strong correlation. However, the Sig. (2-tailed) value obtained is 0.063, which is greater than 0.05. This indicates that the correlation is not statistically significant. Thus, hypothesis 7 which indicates a positive relationship between switching costs and user loyalty is unacceptable. Although the Pearson correlation (r) value indicates a very strong positive relationship between the two variables, the correlation is not statistically significant. Therefore, while there is a very strong numerical correlation, the relationship between switching costs and user loyalty cannot be declared empirically significant in the context of a rally B2B e-commerce platform

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it was found that the relationship between the research variables showed mixed results. The Perceived Value relationship to User Loyalty has a strong positive correlation, but is not statistically significant, so this hypothesis is unacceptable. A

similar thing happened with the relationship between Switching Costs and User Loyalty, where although the correlation was numerically strong, the results were not statistically significant, so this hypothesis is also unacceptable.

Meanwhile, the relationship between Service Quality and User Loyalty shows a strong and statistically significant positive correlation, so this hypothesis is accepted. This confirms that improving service quality can contribute significantly to increasing user loyalty. In addition, the relationship between User Satisfaction and User Loyalty shows a very strong and statistically significant correlation. These findings reinforce the fact that higher user satisfaction levels contribute directly to increased user loyalty towards b2b platform e-commerce applications.

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